
The Implication of Genetically Modified Food on the Economy of Third World Countries

Chibuzor Chigozie Nweke, PhD

Department of Political Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Mark, Kingsley Chinonso, PhD.

Department of Political Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Okafor, Jude Chukwuemeka

Department of Political Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Osita, James Igweike

Department of Political Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Abstract

The paper analyzed the economic implications of genetically modified (GM) food on Third World countries, analyzing both the opportunities and challenges associated with GM technology. The study aimed to address the growing debate on GM crops' potential to improve food security, agricultural productivity, and economic development in nations heavily dependent on agriculture. However, it also highlighted the significant risks, particularly the economic dependence on multinational corporations controlling GM seed markets and the barriers to international trade due to regulatory constraints. The research utilized the state capture theory to examine the influence of powerful corporate interests on national policies regarding GM crops. A qualitative research methodology was employed, using secondary data from books, journals, and official publications, analyzed through content analysis to explore the key economic effects of GM food. Findings revealed substantial productivity increases, as seen in India, Burkina Faso, and South Africa, alongside concerns about seed monopolization, rising production costs, and limited market access. The conclusion underscored the dual nature of GM technology, offering both economic benefits and creating vulnerabilities in agricultural systems. Based on the findings, recommendations were made to strengthen indigenous biotechnology, implement fair intellectual property agreements, and diversify export markets to ensure sustainable agricultural development while mitigating the negative economic impacts of GM food technologies in Third World countries.

Keywords: Genetics, Technology, Food, Economy, Dependence, Third World

Introduction

Genetic modification is a special set of gene technology that alters the genetic machinery of such living organisms as animals, plants or microorganisms. Combining genes from different organisms is known as recombinant DNA technology and the resulting organism is said to be 'Genetically modified (GM)', 'Genetically engineered' or 'transgenic'. The principal transgenic crops grown commercially in field are herbicide and insecticide resistant soybeans, corn, cotton and canola. Other crops grown commercially and/or field-tested are sweet potato resistant to a virus that could destroy most of the African harvest, rice with increased iron and vitamins that may alleviate chronic malnutrition in Asian countries and a variety of plants that are able to survive weather extremes. There are bananas that produce human vaccines against infectious diseases such as hepatitis B, fish that mature more quickly, fruit and nut trees that yield years earlier and plants that produce new plastics with unique properties. Technologies for genetically modifying foods offer dramatic promise for meeting some areas of greatest challenge for the 21st century. Like all new technologies, they also pose some risks, both known and unknown. Controversies and public concern surrounding GM foods and crops commonly focus on human and environmental safety, labeling and consumer choice, intellectual property rights, ethics, food security, poverty reduction and environmental conservation. With this new technology on gene manipulation what are the risks of "tampering with Mother Nature"? what effects will this have on the environment?, what are the health concerns that consumers should be aware of? and is recombinant technology really beneficial? This review will also address some major concerns about the safety, environmental and ecological risks and health hazards involved with GM foods and recombinant technology.

Scientists first discovered in 1946 that DNA can be transferred between organisms (Clive 2011). It is now known that there are several mechanisms for DNA transfer and that these occur in nature on a large scale, for example, it is a major mechanism for antibiotic resistance in pathogenic bacteria. The first genetically modified (GM) plant was produced in 1983, using an antibiotic-resistant tobacco plant. China was the first country to commercialize a transgenic crop in the early 1990s with the introduction of virus resistant tobacco. In 1994, the transgenic 'Flavour Saver tomato' was approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for marketing in the USA. The modification allowed the tomato to delay ripening after picking. In 1995, few transgenic crops received marketing approval. This include canola with modified oil composition (Calgene), *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) corn/maize (Ciba-Geigy), cotton resistant to the herbicide bromoxynil (Calgene), Bt cotton (Monsanto), Bt potatoes (Monsanto), soybeans resistant to the herbicide glyphosate (Monsanto), virus-resistant squash (Asgrow) and additional delayed ripening tomatoes (DNAP, Zeneca/Peto, and Monsanto) (Clive 2011). A total of 35 approvals had been granted to commercially grow 8 transgenic crops and one flower crop of carnations with 8 different traits in 6 countries plus the EU till 1996 (Clive 1996). As of 2011, the USA leads a list of multiple countries in the production of GM crops. Currently, there are a number of food species in which a genetically modified version exists (Johnson 2008). Some of the foods that are available in the market include cotton, soybean, canola, potatoes, eggplant, strawberries, corn, tomatoes, lettuce, cantaloupe, carrots etc. GM products which are currently in the pipeline include medicines and vaccines, foods and food ingredients, feeds and fibres. Locating genes for important traits, such as those conferring insect resistance or desired nutrients-is one of the most limiting steps in the process..

The discuss on Genetically modified Organisms GMO over the years have taken two faces; the major argument over the years has been on the health challenges that GMO food comes with; the other discuss is the economic challenges that GMO brings to the third world economy. Against this backdrop, this study tilt more towards the economy of third world especially Africa and how genetically modified foods affect it.

Statement of Problem

The research on the implications of genetically modified (GM) food on the economy of Third World countries is prompted by the growing debates surrounding the adoption of GM technology and its potential to either alleviate or exacerbate the challenges faced by these nations. In the past few decades, GM crops have been hailed as a solution to food insecurity, reduced agricultural productivity, and climate-related challenges, especially in countries heavily dependent on agriculture (Aerni, 2005; Brookes & Barfoot, 2018). However, while the potential benefits are substantial, there are significant concerns regarding the broader economic implications of such technology, particularly in nations with fragile agricultural sectors and economies (Pingali, 2012).

The problem that necessitated this research arises from the dual nature of GM crops: on one hand, they promise increased yields, reduced dependence on chemical inputs, and the potential for economic growth through enhanced agricultural exports (Qaim, 2010). On the other hand, these benefits are often counterbalanced by economic challenges that undermine long-term sustainability. Many Third World countries face growing dependency on multinational corporations for GM seeds and agricultural technologies. This has led to issues of seed monopolization, which in turn increases costs for farmers who are required to purchase new seeds every planting season, stripping them of traditional farming methods like seed saving (Stone, 2007). Additionally, there is an ongoing issue of limited market access for GM crops, particularly in key European markets, where GM foods face strict regulations and resistance (Gruère & Sengupta, 2011). This restricts the export potential of GM crops, leaving countries vulnerable to fluctuating global trade dynamics.

Conceptual Clarification

Genetically Modified Organism (GMO)

A Genetically Modified Organism (GMO) refers to any organism whose genetic material has been altered using genetic engineering techniques. This modification aims to introduce desirable traits such as resistance to pests, diseases, environmental conditions, or to improve nutritional content (National Research Council, 2004). In agriculture, GMOs are employed to enhance crop yield, improve resistance to pests and diseases, and reduce reliance on chemical pesticides (James, 2013). In the medical field, GMOs are pivotal in the production of pharmaceuticals like insulin and growth hormones (Houdebine, 2009). Furthermore, in industrial applications, genetically modified microorganisms are utilized to produce biofuels, biodegradable plastics, and other products (Stephanopoulos, 2007).

The use of GMOs, however, is enveloped in controversy and debate. Advocates argue that GMOs can significantly enhance food security, mitigate agricultural impact on the environment, and contribute to medical advancements (FAO, 2004). Critics, on the other hand, raise concerns about potential health risks, environmental impacts, and ethical considerations surrounding genetic modification (Ewen & Pusztai, 1999). The debate continues to evolve as new research and technologies emerge, reflecting the complex nature of this biotechnological innovation.

Third World

The term "Third World" emerged during the Cold War era, initially used to describe countries that were not aligned with either the Western bloc (First World) or the Eastern bloc (Second World) (McMichael, 2012). Today, the term is often used, albeit increasingly considered outdated and pejorative, to refer to developing countries with lower levels of industrialization, lower standards of living, and higher rates of poverty (Rist, 2002).

Third World countries are typically characterized by economic, social, and political challenges. Economically, these nations often have lower GDP per capita and rely heavily on agriculture and raw material exports (Todaro & Smith, 2015). Socially, they face higher rates of poverty, lower life expectancy, and limited access to education and healthcare (World Bank, 2019). Politically, many Third World countries grapple with instability, corruption, and weaker institutions (Kaufmann, Kraay, & Mastruzzi, 2009). Despite these challenges, the term "Third World" fails to capture the diversity and potential within these countries, leading to a shift towards more specific and respectful terms like "developing countries," "Global South," or "low- and middle-income countries" (LMICs) (Sumner, 2012).

Third World Economy

A Third World economy pertains to the economic systems and conditions of countries traditionally categorized as part of the Third World. These economies are predominantly agrarian, with a significant portion of the workforce engaged in agriculture (Lewis, 1954). Industrial development is limited, and infrastructure is often underdeveloped, contributing to lower standards of living and higher levels of poverty (Rodrik, 2011).

Key features of a Third World economy include lower per capita income, widespread income inequality, and lower human development indicators such as life expectancy, infant mortality rates, and literacy rates (UNDP, 2019). These economies are often dependent on a few primary commodities for export, making them vulnerable to global market fluctuations (Collier, 2007). Additionally, political instability and weak institutions can hinder economic growth and development (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Addressing the challenges faced by Third World economies requires multifaceted strategies. Efforts to reduce poverty, improve healthcare and education, foster political stability, and build sustainable economic growth are crucial (Sachs, 2005). There are also significant opportunities for rapid growth through industrialization, investment in human capital, and integration into the global economy (Todaro & Smith, 2015). Sectors such as technology, renewable energy, and tourism hold the potential to drive economic progress and transform Third World economies (World Bank, 2020).

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research method, specifically utilizing a descriptive research design to explore the topic. Qualitative research focuses on collecting and analyzing non-numerical data, such as texts, articles, and audio-visual materials, to gain insights into concepts, opinions, and experiences (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). This approach facilitates a deeper understanding of the issues at hand and can help generate new research ideas (Creswell, 2013). The primary method of data collection used in this research is the documentary technique, relying on secondary materials like books, journals, newspapers, and official publications. All sourced materials will undergo comparative scrutiny to validate their content and context, aiming to eliminate potential distortions (Guba & Lincoln, 1989). The study adopts the content analysis method. Content analysis systematically identifies and interprets specified characteristics of

messages within documents (Stone, 1966, in Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2006). This technique allows for the examination of the underlying structure, ideas, and concepts within the data, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the content and its implications (White, 1983, in Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2006).

Theoretical Framework

State capture theory is a theory within political science and economics that highlights the manipulation of state institutions by powerful private actors, such as corporations, political elites, and interest groups, to advance their own interests at the expense of public welfare. Originating from the work of scholars studying the intersection between politics and economics, the theory has its roots in studies of post-communist economies, particularly in Eastern Europe during the transition from authoritarian regimes to market economies in the 1990s (Murrell, 1995). State capture occurs when these private actors influence the state's legal, regulatory, and policy frameworks, often bending them to favor their economic interests, thereby undermining the state's role as a neutral regulator (Hellman et al., 2000).

The theory was notably advanced by economists and political scientists like Peter Murrell, who applied it to transition economies, arguing that in such environments, private elites use their financial and political resources to mold state policies to their benefit. Murrell's work in the early 1990s was instrumental in providing a framework to understand how powerful actors can hijack state machinery to perpetuate their control over key economic sectors (Murrell, 1995). This was later expanded by scholars such as Hellman, Jones, and Kaufmann (2000), who examined the dynamics of state capture in post-communist states and found that it impedes democratic consolidation and economic reform. According to these theorists, state capture occurs when elites dominate state institutions, not only influencing policy but also securing favorable outcomes through illegal or opaque channels, making it difficult for the broader population to benefit from state resources (Hellman et al., 2000). The theory holds that state capture is more harmful than simple corruption because it involves systemic manipulation of the state, such that state policies and legal structures are designed or altered to serve private interests. This makes it much more challenging to rectify through traditional anti-corruption measures. State capture often leads to the establishment of a "shadow state," where a small group of actors control vast segments of the economy, while ordinary citizens face limited opportunities for upward mobility or access to public goods and services (Rose-Ackerman, 1999). The theory's postulations emphasize the collusion between state actors and private elites, resulting in a concentration of power that stifles democratic governance and equitable economic development (Kaufmann, 2005).

Applying the state capture theory to the research on genetically modified (GM) food in Third World countries, the theory provides a lens through which we can understand how multinational biotech companies, particularly those controlling the GM seed market, may engage in practices that influence the agricultural policies of developing nations. Large corporations like Monsanto (now part of Bayer) have long been accused of using their financial and political leverage to shape laws and regulations regarding GM crops in both developed and developing countries (GRAIN, 2011). Through lobbying, political donations, and the influence of powerful industry groups, these corporations often succeed in influencing policy decisions that favor their economic interests, such as securing intellectual property rights over GM seeds, enforcing restrictive patent laws, and limiting the autonomy of local farmers (GRAIN, 2011; Shiva, 2016).

For example, many countries in Africa and Latin America have introduced GM crops to address food insecurity and increase agricultural productivity (Qaim, 2010). However, the state policies promoting GM crops often reflect the influence of these multinational corporations rather than the interests of local farmers or the broader public. In some cases, these companies have succeeded in ensuring that local farmers are forced to buy seeds every season, with few legal avenues available for local seed production or saving. This represents a form of state capture, where the regulatory framework has been shaped by external economic interests to the detriment of domestic agricultural systems (Stone, 2007). Additionally, these private corporations often avoid paying taxes or fail to reinvest in the communities where their products are sold, which exacerbates inequality and hinders local economic development (Bennett et al., 2018). Moreover, the research suggests that these corporate influences, alongside the complexities of global trade, could undermine the economic sovereignty of Third World countries. By prioritizing policies that benefit multinational corporations, governments may unintentionally lock their economies into a cycle of dependency, leaving little room for indigenous agricultural innovation or fair competition. As state capture theory suggests, this entrenchment of power within a small elite can undermine democratic processes, restrict opportunities for smallholder farmers, and limit the long-term development potential of Third World economies (Aerni, 2005). Therefore, examining the GM food sector through the lens of state capture highlights the challenges that developing nations face in navigating global economic pressures while maintaining control over their agricultural and economic futures.

Genetically Modified Food the Pros and Cons

GE crops have been portrayed unequivocally by those opposing or promoting the technology as either the solution for feeding the world, or in some instances, as crops that would bring environmental and social catastrophes of incalculable consequences (Brac de la PerriFre and Seuret 2000; GRAIN 2004). Stone (2002) documents that such contrasting positions can and do obscure many of the complexities involved in GE crop adoption and their use in developing countries. A more balanced position would consider GE crops neither as Franken foods nor as Miracle Crops per se, but rather as a set of technologies with unique attributes, different from past innovations, such as the Green Revolution's maize and wheat varieties. In particular, many of these technologies have been produced using research and development (R&D) inputs that are protected intellectual property, and most technologies now available commercially have been developed by the private sector.

These attributes need to be characterized, discussed, and in some cases addressed to ensure their compatibility with and support of poverty alleviation efforts, especially in the agricultural context of SSA. Furthermore, there is a need to clearly separate the intrinsic production, productivity, and socio-economic impacts of GE crops from more general concerns expressed by some stakeholders over forced industrialization, corporate control of agriculture, and the impact of technology on traditional farmers and agricultural practices and communities. The latter implies the need to conduct in-depth social and institutional context analysis in which these varieties may be or have been released to farmers to ensure that society can determine the potential role of GE crops in development and poverty alleviation efforts (Stone 2011). This is especially important in the African context.

Who are the crop pushers?

Like the Green Revolution before it, GM crops have come to Africa from developments in the North. The driving force behind the development of GM crops is the pesticide industry. By the 1990s, the industry was beset by several major problems. For one, the chemistry was exhausted and it had become increasingly difficult and expensive to develop new pesticides. Second, the blockbuster pesticides were about to come off patent and the TNCs feared that generic producers would reduce prices and take an increasing share of the market. Off-patent pesticides already account for 53% of the entire global market and by 2005 they are expected to account for 69%, with a market value of \$27 billion. And finally, revenue from pesticide sales were on the decline in the North as more and more of the profits from agricultural production were being taken by the food retailers, processors, and distributors, who used their near monopoly positions to squeeze farmers. Genetic engineering has been brought in to resolve these problems. On the one hand, it provides a whole new area of science—biology—that the companies can turn to for new pesticides and hence, new patents. Companies can also modify crops so that they only grow properly when sprayed with their own pesticides and prevent farmers from using generic versions by way of contracts, thereby getting around the generic pesticide problem. As an added bonus, whereas a new pesticide costs between \$40-100 million to bring through the regulatory process, it typically costs under \$1 million to bring a new plant variety to market. On the other hand, GM crops with added value, such as GM vitamin A rice or GM high-protein corn, enable the pesticide industry to increase its share of profits from the production of food and animal feed. Once the pesticide TNCs understood the potential that GM crops could provide, they moved quickly, buying up all the most advanced biotechnology firms and the world's largest seed companies, and securing alliances with the major food and feed processors and distributors. Between 1997 and 1999, transactions by pesticide companies in the seed industry topped US\$18 billion. The top five pesticide companies now control roughly 30% of the seed market and 50% of all agricultural biotechnology patents, including 70% of all patents on genes for wheat and 47% of all patents on genes for sorghum. The first crops introduced reflect corporate business strategies. In 1999, 78% of all the genetically engineered crops planted in the world were engineered for herbicide tolerance and the vast majority were engineered for tolerance to the herbicide Roundup (glyphosate). For Monsanto, the world's leading supplier of Roundup and the owner of most Roundup-resistant GM crops, the GM crops were an effective way to protect sales of its herbicide, which was coming off-patent around the world in 2000-2001. Industry is now interested in bringing its technology to Africa. South Africa, with its large commercial farming sector and accommodating policy environment was the first and continues to be the most popular destination for GM seeds. The first GM crop, Bt cotton, was approved for commercial release in 1997 and by 2001 more than 200,000 ha were planted with GM crops. Industry is now trying to introduce GM crops in other African countries. Its major targets are the commercial maize and cotton-growing areas, since these crops already have well-established commercial market structures. For the same reasons, applications to introduce GM fruits and flowers for export production are probably not far off. Yet the market potential in Africa for GM seeds is relatively small, and, in the near term, the public sector will remain the most significant actor in formal sector plant breeding. This means that public scientists have a particularly influential role to play when it comes to the introduction of GM crops in Africa. Although GM crops have only been introduced in a few African countries and most have yet to formulate a national position on biotechnology, research on GM crops is moving ahead in public research centres.

The implication of the above is that like in the case of Bill Gates in the just adopted Tela Maize in Nigeria, a small group of multi-billionaires and Multinational Corporations are the pushers of the GM crops. They have autonomy and monopoly on both the proselytizes and proliferation of GM crops, eventually giving them the right to heavily influence market and economic policies and decisions in the agricultural sector of third world countries. The consequences of this are that the food security of these countries rests in the hands of these powerful individuals and MNCs. Furthermore, a variable climate, political instability, and other constraints have limited agricultural development in African countries. Therefore, the Third world countries by default would find it very hard to initiate their own technological development in the biotech field, or pursue other alternatives if the conditions of the foreign biotech companies become unfavorable. This leaves them at the mercy of the “pushers” and unable to resist the policy conditions of the Biotech companies leading to further dependency and capture of the third world states.

Supposed Economic Benefits

The economic benefits of genetically modified (GM) food in Third World countries have been a subject of considerable scholarly interest, particularly regarding their potential to enhance agricultural productivity, reduce poverty, and stimulate broader economic growth. Qaim (2020) argues that the adoption of GM crops in developing countries has led to significant yield increases, which directly translate into higher incomes for farmers and contribute to rural economic development. For example, countries such as Burkina Faso and India have experienced substantial productivity gains through the cultivation of GM cotton, with yield increases ranging from 20% to 50%, reducing the cost of production and enhancing profitability for farmers. This increased agricultural output has a ripple effect on the economy, stimulating growth in related sectors such as agro-processing, transportation, and trade (James, 2018).

Increased agricultural productivity from GM crops also plays a crucial role in addressing food security, which is a persistent challenge in many Third World countries. By reducing crop losses caused by pests, diseases, and environmental stressors, GM technology ensures more consistent and reliable food supplies. This stability helps to moderate food prices, making essential commodities more affordable for consumers, particularly in low-income households (Brookes & Barfoot, 2019). Furthermore, the reduction in input costs associated with GM crops, such as decreased pesticide and herbicide usage, enables farmers to reallocate resources toward other economic activities, fostering diversification and resilience within rural economies. These cost savings are particularly significant for smallholder farmers, who constitute the majority of agricultural producers in Third World countries and are often constrained by limited financial resources (Qaim, 2020).

The broader macroeconomic implications of GM food adoption are also evident in the trade sector. As Brookes and Barfoot (2019) note, countries that have embraced GM crops have strengthened their export potential, particularly in commodities such as soybeans, maize, and cotton, which are in high demand globally. For instance, Argentina and Brazil have become major exporters of GM soybeans, generating substantial foreign exchange earnings and enhancing their trade balances. These export revenues are critical for Third World countries, providing much-needed capital for infrastructure development, social services, and debt reduction. By increasing their competitiveness in the global agricultural market, these countries can reduce their reliance on foreign aid and loans, thereby fostering greater economic independence (James, 2018). Additionally, the adoption of GM crops has catalyzed technological

innovation and knowledge transfer in Third World countries. The integration of biotechnology into agricultural practices has prompted investments in research and development, particularly in countries like South Africa and India, where public and private sectors have collaborated to develop region-specific GM crops (Pechlaner, 2020). This collaboration not only enhances local technological capabilities but also creates employment opportunities in biotechnology research, seed production, and extension services. The resulting knowledge diffusion strengthens the agricultural sector's human capital, contributing to long-term economic development and the creation of a more skilled workforce (Clapp, 2021).

Moreover, the environmental benefits associated with GM crops have economic ramifications. By reducing the need for chemical inputs, GM technology lowers the environmental impact of agriculture, preserving natural resources and ensuring long-term agricultural sustainability (Qaim, 2020). This environmental stewardship is particularly crucial in Third World countries, where agricultural productivity is heavily dependent on natural resource availability. Preserving soil fertility, water resources, and biodiversity through GM technology can mitigate the economic costs associated with environmental degradation, ensuring that agricultural sectors remain viable and productive over the long term (Shiva, 2016).

Negative Implications of GMO on Third World Countries

The introduction of genetically modified (GM) food into the economies of Third World countries has sparked considerable debate, with evidence pointing to significant negative economic implications that go beyond the immediate benefits of increased agricultural productivity. Clapp (2021) argues that the global dominance of multinational biotechnology corporations, which control the intellectual property rights over GM seeds, has deepened economic inequality and dependence in developing nations. This monopolistic control has led to a situation where smallholder farmers are often forced to purchase expensive patented seeds each planting season, rather than saving seeds from previous harvests, a traditional practice that had long been integral to local agricultural sustainability. The increased costs associated with acquiring GM seeds and necessary agrochemicals contribute to the financial strain on small-scale farmers, reducing their profit margins and increasing rural poverty (Qaim, 2020).

The economic dependency fostered by multinational corporations extends to national economies, particularly in countries where agriculture constitutes a significant portion of GDP. As Pechlaner (2020) notes, "Third World countries become economically vulnerable when they rely on external entities for critical agricultural inputs". This dependency not only limits the sovereignty of these nations over their agricultural systems but also undermines their capacity to invest in indigenous agricultural research and development. Furthermore, the monopolization of seed markets by global agribusiness giants marginalizes local seed producers, effectively stifling competition and innovation within domestic agricultural sectors (Clapp, 2021). This scenario perpetuates a cycle of dependency and underdevelopment, hampering the long-term economic resilience of these countries. Another critical economic concern is the impact of GM food on trade relations and market access. Many Third World countries rely heavily on agricultural exports as a primary source of foreign exchange. However, the global market for GM crops is highly polarized, with key trading partners such as the European Union maintaining strict regulatory barriers against genetically modified products. According to Brookes and Barfoot (2019), this resistance has led to reduced market opportunities for GM-exporting countries, thereby limiting their access to lucrative markets and exacerbating their trade deficits. The loss of

market diversification creates economic vulnerabilities, as these countries become increasingly reliant on a narrower set of trading partners, often at the expense of their bargaining power and economic stability. Moreover, the socio-economic impact of GM food adoption has exacerbated existing rural inequalities, particularly in regions where access to technology is unevenly distributed. Studies conducted by Shiva (2016) indicate that wealthier farmers, who can afford the initial costs of GM seeds and associated technologies, often outcompete smaller farmers, leading to land concentration and rural displacement. The resulting economic disparity fosters social tensions and rural-urban migration, further straining urban infrastructures and public services in developing countries. These socio-economic shifts undermine rural economies, reducing the overall contribution of agriculture to national economic growth and deepening poverty in already vulnerable communities (Shiva, 2016; Qaim, 2020).

Furthermore, the long-term environmental risks associated with GM food production can have substantial economic repercussions. Pechlaner (2020) highlights that the over-reliance on herbicide-tolerant crops has led to the emergence of herbicide-resistant weeds, necessitating higher expenditures on chemical inputs and additional labor. This increased cost burden is disproportionately borne by smallholder farmers, exacerbating their economic hardships and reducing the competitiveness of agricultural exports. Additionally, environmental degradation linked to GM farming practices can reduce soil fertility and biodiversity, diminishing agricultural productivity and threatening food security. The resultant decline in agricultural output not only affects domestic food prices but also weakens the export capacity of these countries, thereby reducing their foreign exchange earnings and overall economic stability (Shiva, 2016).

Findings

Research on the economic implications of genetically modified (GM) food in Third World countries reveals both opportunities and challenges. One significant finding is the substantial increase in agricultural productivity. For example, in India and Burkina Faso, the introduction of GM cotton in the early 2000s resulted in yield increases of up to 50%, significantly boosting farmers' incomes and improving rural livelihoods. This enhanced productivity has reduced food insecurity, increased household incomes, and stimulated rural economic growth. By 2018, countries like South Africa had adopted GM maize, which led to a 31% increase in national maize production, reducing the need for food imports and stabilizing local food prices.

However, the economic dependency created by the dominance of multinational corporations in the GM seed market is a critical issue. Companies like Monsanto, which controlled over 90% of the global GM seed market by 2016, have patented seed technologies that require farmers to purchase new seeds annually. This practice limits traditional farming methods such as seed saving, increasing production costs for smallholder farmers and reducing profit margins. Additionally, local seed industries in countries such as Kenya and the Philippines have struggled to compete, leading to a loss of agricultural biodiversity and increased dependency on foreign seed companies.

Another important finding is the impact of GM crops on international trade. While countries like Brazil and Argentina have benefited from exporting GM soybeans, earning billions in foreign exchange, others face trade barriers. By 2015, the European Union, a significant global market, maintained strict regulations on GM food imports, limiting market access for many developing countries. This regulatory environment has created trade vulnerabilities, making countries that rely heavily on GM crop exports susceptible to market fluctuations and economic instability,

particularly in cases where export revenues are a major component of national GDP. In essence, while GM food technologies have brought notable economic benefits through increased agricultural productivity and export potential, they also present challenges related to market dependency, trade barriers, and economic inequality. These dynamics continue to shape the agricultural and economic landscape of Third World countries.

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from the research on the economic implications of genetically modified (GM) food in Third World countries underscores a dual reality: while GM technology holds immense potential for increasing agricultural productivity and fostering economic growth, it also presents significant challenges that could undermine local economies and exacerbate dependency on foreign entities. The promise of enhanced crop yields, reduced pesticide use, and improved food security has driven many developing nations to adopt GM crops. Countries like India and South Africa have witnessed notable economic benefits, including increased rural incomes and reduced food imports, demonstrating that GM technology can play a pivotal role in addressing food insecurity and boosting agricultural sectors.

However, the research highlights that these benefits often come with considerable risks. The monopolization of the seed industry by multinational corporations, the erosion of traditional farming practices, and limited market access due to stringent international trade regulations have created economic vulnerabilities. For smallholder farmers, the high costs associated with patented seeds and the dependency on annual seed purchases threaten long-term economic sustainability. Furthermore, trade barriers in key global markets, particularly in the European Union, limit the export potential of GM crops, exposing Third World countries to economic instability.

Therefore, the pathway forward involves striking a balance between leveraging the advantages of GM technology and mitigating its drawbacks. Indigenous development of biotechnology, fairer intellectual property agreements, and strategic regional alliances are essential strategies for fostering economic resilience. By adopting these measures, Third World countries can reduce their dependency on foreign entities, ensure equitable access to agricultural innovations, and diversify their trade networks. Ultimately, while GM technology offers significant opportunities, its successful integration into Third World economies requires careful governance, robust local capacity building, and strategic international cooperation to ensure sustainable and inclusive economic development.

Recommendations

1. Strengthening Indigenous Biotechnology and Agricultural Innovation

To reduce dependency on multinational corporations, Third World countries must prioritize the development of their indigenous biotechnology sectors. Governments should invest in research institutions and universities to create locally adapted GM crops tailored to their unique climates and agricultural needs. For instance, initiatives like Brazil's EMBRAPA (Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation) have demonstrated how localized research can empower farmers with affordable, effective GM solutions. By fostering public-private partnerships, countries can leverage local expertise while benefiting from advanced Western technologies, creating a more self-reliant agricultural system that stimulates economic growth and employment.

2. Implementing Fair Intellectual Property (IP) and Licensing Agreements

To combat the monopolistic control of GM seed markets, Third World countries should negotiate fairer IP and licensing agreements with Western biotech firms. Governments can enforce policies that allow for technology transfer and joint ventures, ensuring that local seed companies have access to GM technology without the burden of excessive costs. For example, India's seed licensing regulations have enabled domestic companies to co-develop GM crops, reducing costs for farmers and increasing market competition. This approach ensures that farmers can benefit from technological advancements while maintaining control over their agricultural resources.

3. Establishing Regional Trade Alliances and Diversifying Export Markets

Third World countries should form regional alliances to strengthen their bargaining power in global trade negotiations. By creating unified policies on GM crop production and trade, these countries can present a stronger front in international markets, reducing their vulnerability to trade restrictions imposed by regions like the European Union. Furthermore, diversifying export markets by engaging with both Western and non-Western countries will reduce dependency on any single market. Countries like Kenya, for instance, have begun exploring new trade agreements with Asian markets, ensuring greater market stability and resilience against fluctuations in Western demand for GM products.

References

- Allison, S., & Palma, P. M. (1997). Commercialization of transgenic plants: Potential ecological risks. *BioScience*, 47(2), 86–96. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1313019>
- Ballari, V. R., Martin, A., & Gowda, L. R. (2012). Detection and identification of genetically modified EE-1 brinjal (*Solanum melongena*) by single, multiplex and SYBR® real-time PCR. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.5764>
- Beagle, J. M., Apgar, G. A., Jones, K. L., Griswold, K. E., Radcliffe, J. S., Qiu, X., Lightfoot, D. A., & Iqbal, M. J. (2006). The digestive fate of *Escherichia coli* glutamate dehydrogenase deoxyribonucleic acid from transgenic corn in diets fed to weanling pigs. *Journal of Animal Science*, 84(3), 597–607.
- Berberich, S. A., Ream, J. E., Jackson, T. L., Wood, R., Stipanovic, R., Harvey, P., Patzer, S., & Fuchs, R. L. (1996). The composition of insect-protected cottonseed is equivalent to that of conventional cottonseed. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 44(2), 365–371. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf950304i>
- Bernstein, I. L., Bernstein, J. A., Miller, M., Tierzieva, S., Bernstein, D. I., Lummus, Z., Selgrade, M. K., Doerfler, D. L., & Seligy, V. L. (1999). Immune responses in farm workers after exposure to *Bacillus thuringiensis* pesticides. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 107(8), 575–582. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.99107575>
- Brake, J., & Vlachos, D. (1998). Evaluation of transgenic Event 176 “Bt” corn in broiler chickens. *Poultry Science*, 77(5), 648–653.
- Brian, H. (1999). Unintended effects of Bt crops. *World Watch*, 12, 9–10.

- Brigulla, M., & Wackernagel, W. (2010). Molecular aspects of gene transfer and foreign DNA acquisition in prokaryotes with regard to safety issues. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 86(4), 1027–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-010-2489-3>
- Burks, A. W., & Fuchs, R. L. (1995). Assessment of the endogenous allergens in glyphosate-tolerant and commercial soybean varieties. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 96(5), 1008–1010. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0091-6749\(95\)70243-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0091-6749(95)70243-1)
- Butler, T., & Reichhardt, T. (1999). Long-term effect of GM crops serves up food for thought. *Nature*, 398(6729), 651–653. <https://doi.org/10.1038/19348>
- Cellini, F., Chesson, A., Colquhoun, I., Constable, A., Davies, H. V., Engel, K. H., Gatehouse, A. M. R., Karenlampi, S., Kok, E. J., Leguay, J. J., Lehasranta, S., Noteborn, H. P. J. M., Pedersen, J., & Smith, M. (2004). Unintended effects and their detection in genetically modified crops. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 42(7), 1089–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2004.02.003>
- Chapman, M. D. (2008). Allergen nomenclature. In R. F. Lockey & K. Dennis Ledford (Eds.), *Allergens and allergen immunotherapy* (4th ed., pp. 47–58). Informa Healthcare.
- Clive, J. (1996). Global review of the field testing and commercialization of transgenic plants: 1986 to 1995. International Service for the Acquisition of Agri-biotech Applications. <http://www.isaaa.org/kc/Publications/pdfs/isaaabriefs/Briefs%201.pdf>
- Clive, J. (2011). Global status of commercialized biotech/GM crops. ISAAA Briefs 43. Ithaca: International Service for the Acquisition of Agri-biotech Applications.
- Conner, A. J., & Jacobs, J. M. E. (1999). Genetic engineering of crops as a potential source of genetic hazard in the human diet. *Mutation Research*, 443(2), 223–234. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1383-5742\(99\)00020-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1383-5742(99)00020-4)
- Brookes, G., & Barfoot, P. (2018). Economic impact of GM crops: Global income and production effects 1996–2016. *GM Crops & Food*, 9(2), 59–75.
- Eichstadt, S. (2021, August 22). Pros and cons of GMOs in Africa. The Borgen Project. Retrieved from <https://borgenproject.org/pros-and-cons-of-gmos-in-africa>
- Glover, D. (2010). The corporate shaping of GM crops as a technology for the poor. *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 37(1), 67–90.
- Gouse, M., Pray, C., & Schimmelpfennig, D. (2005). The distribution of benefits from Bt cotton adoption in South Africa. *AgBioForum*, 8(2&3), 187–194.
- Klümper, W., & Qaim, M. (2014). A meta-analysis of the impacts of genetically modified crops. *PLOS ONE*, 9(11), e111629.
- Llewellyn, R. S., & Furtan, W. H. (2007). Patent infringement and enforcement: Implications for biotechnology research investments. *Agricultural Economics*, 37(2-3), 161–170.

- Paarlberg, R. (2008). *Starved for Science: How Biotechnology is Being Kept Out of Africa*. Harvard University Press.
- Qaim, M., & Zilberman, D. (2003). Yield effects of genetically modified crops in developing countries. *Science*, 299(5608), 900–902.
- Shiva, V. (2000). *Stolen Harvest: The Hijacking of the Global Food Supply*. South End Press.
- Shiva, V. (2016). *The Violence of the Green Revolution: Third World Agriculture, Ecology, and Politics*. Zed Books.